

methine proton at position 2 ($-\text{CH}_2-\overset{|}{\text{C}}\text{H}-\text{CH}_2\text{Br}$) and two methylene protons at position 3 ($-\text{CH}_2-\overset{|}{\text{C}}\text{H}-$) of the thiazolidine ring. The four aromatic protons also appeared as a multiplet at 7.20–8.70.

Dehydrohalogenation of IV finally gave rise to the required 2-methylene-3H,10H-thiazolo[2',3':3,4]-s-triazolo[5,1-b]quinazolin-10-one (V). Structure V to this compound has been assigned on the basis of ir and analytical results. In its ir, it showed a band at 890 cm^{-1} due to exocyclic carbon-carbon double bond. Besides, it also showed a band at 1670 cm^{-1} due to cyclic amide.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open glass capillaries in liquid paraffin bath and are uncorrected. IR spectrum was taken on Perkin Elmer grating IR spectrometer 621 in Nujol. PMR spectra were recorded on Varian EM-390 90 MHz spectrometer using TMS as the internal reference.

3-Allyl-1-(2-mercapto-4-oxo-3(4H)quinazolinyl)-2-thiopseudourea (III): A mixture of allyl isothiocyanate (0.30 g) and 3-amino-2-mercaptoquinazolin-4(3H)-one⁶ (0.5 g) was heated on a steam bath for 2 hr. The solid mass was triturated with ethanol (1 ml) and collected under suction. It was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 210° , yield 0.68 g (90%). (Found: N, 19.42. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4\text{OS}_2$ requires N, 19.18%).

2-Bromomethyl-2,3-dihydro-10H-thiazolo[2',3':3,4]-s-triazolo[5,1-b]quinazolin-10-one (IV): A solution of bromine (0.26 ml) in glacial acetic acid (1 ml) was added dropwise with constant stirring to a cold solution of III (0.152 g) in 10 ml of the same solvent. The contents were kept at room temp. overnight and then heated on a water bath for 1 hr. It was cooled and the product collected under suction. It was crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 240° , yield 0.123 g (70%). (Found: C, 43.37; H, 2.90. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_9\text{BrN}_4\text{OS}$ requires C, 43.03; H, 2.67%).

2-Methylene-3H,10H-thiazolo[2',3':3,4]-s-triazolo[5,1-b]quinazolin-10-one (V): 2% Alcoholic potassium hydroxide was added to a solution of IV (0.1 g) in ethanol at 40° . This temp. was maintained for about 20 min. Ice was added to it after cooling to room temperature. The solid product so

obtained was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 220° , yield 0.032 g (42%). (Found: C, 56.00; H, 3.24. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_8\text{N}_4\text{OS}$ requires C, 56.25; H, 3.12%).

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Professor M. L. Lakhnanpal, Chairman, Department of Chemistry for his interest and to Shri Avtar Singh for running the nmr spectra of the compounds.

References

1. F. BRODY and M. T. BOGERT, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **65**, 1080.
2. M. L. MERCURY, S. M. VINCENT and M. L. SHERRILL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, **68**, 1894.
3. A. BURGER and G. E. ULLYOT, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1947, **12**, 342.
4. H. D. TROUTMAN and L. M. LONG, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 3436.
5. H. K. GAKHAR, S. O. GUPTA and N. KUMAR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1981, **20B**, 14.

Experiments with Coumarins. Part-I :

Synthesis of 3,5-Disubstituted Isoxazoles and Pyrazoles

P. M. BAND, N. L. GOKHALE and V. S. JAMODE
Department of Chemistry, Vidarbha Mahavidyalaya,
Amravati-444 604

Manuscript received 18 March 1982, revised 18 October 1982,
accepted 10 March 1983

1-Coumaryl-3-arylpropane-1,3-diones and γ -pyrones of coumarins possess physiological activities¹⁻³. Isoxazole derivatives are important as potential antibacterial⁴, antitubercular⁵ and antiviral agents. In view of this, interest in the synthesis of these compounds developed considerably. Present work deals with the synthesis of isoxazoles (II, III), pyrazoles (IV, V) and γ -pyrones (VI, VII) of coumarins.

o-Hydroxyacetyl coumarins were used as starting materials. 7-Hydroxy-8-acetyl-4-methylcoumarin and 5-hydroxy-6-acetyl-4-methylcoumarin were prepared according to literature⁷⁻¹¹. Esters of *o*-hydroxyacetyl coumarins were prepared by esterification with aromatic acids. These esters, on Baker-Venkataraman transformation, were converted to 1-coumaryl-3-arylpropane-1,3-diones (I). 3,5-Disubstituted isoxazoles (II, III) and pyrazoles (IV, V) were prepared by refluxing the mixture of propane-1,3-diones (I) with hydroxylamine hydrochloride and phenylhydrazine hydrochloride, respectively. Propane-1,3-diones (I) cyclized to afford γ -pyrones (VI, VII) in acetic acid medium.

IR spectra of isoxazole showed absorption bands at $1645\text{--}1650\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\text{C}=\text{N}-\text{O}$), 940 cm^{-1} ($=\text{N}-\text{O}$) and 840 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{C}$).

Experimental

The melting points reported are uncorrected. The ir spectra were run in nujol mull on Unicam SP 200 G grating spectrometer.

Preparation of the esters: To an ice-cold mixture of *o*-hydroxyacetylcoumarin (0.04 mole), dry pyridine (10 ml) and aromatic acid (0.04 mole), POCl₃ (3 ml) was added slowly with constant stirring. The reaction mixture was kept for 7 hr at room temp., then poured over crushed ice containing acetic acid. The solid obtained was filtered and washed with sodium hydroxide (2%) and water. The product was crystallized from ethanol.

Preparation of 1-coumaryl-3-arylpropane-1,3-diones (I): Ester (0.04 mole), dry pyridine (10 ml) and molten KOH (3.4 g) were mixed and the reaction mixture was kept overnight. It was then acidified with ice-cold HCl (1:1). The yellow solid obtained was separated, washed with NaHCO₃ (2%) followed by water and crystallized from ethanol-acetic acid mixture.

Preparation of 3-coumaryl-5-arylisoxazoles (II, III): A mixture of I (0.01 mole) and hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.02 mole) was refluxed in pyridine (10 ml) for 2 hr. The reaction mixture was diluted with water and acidified with acetic acid. The solid product obtained was filtered and crystallized from ethanol (60%).

Preparation of 3-coumaryl-5-aryl-1-phenylpyrazoles (IV, V): A mixture of I (0.01 mole) and phenylhydrazine hydrochloride was refluxed in acetic acid for 2 hr. The reaction mixture was diluted with water. The product obtained was crystallized from ethanol-acetic acid mixture.

For I to VII

- (a) R = H
(b) R = OCH₃

Preparation of γ -pyrones (VI, VII): 1-Coumaryl-3-arylpropane-1,3-dione (I) (0.04 mole) was refluxed in acetic acid (15 ml) containing a few drops of conc. HCl for 0.5 hr. The reaction mixture was poured in water. The solid product obtained was separated and crystallized from ethanol-acetic acid mixture.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF 3-COUMARYL-5-ARYLISOXAZOLES (II, III) AND 3-COUMARYL-5-ARYLPYRAZOLES (IV, V)

Compound	Yield %	m.p. °C	%Nitrogen Found/(Calcd.)*
IIa	50	265	4.49 (4.53)
IIb	60	250	3.98 (4.10)
IIIa	70	252	4.47 (4.53)
IIIb	65	258	3.89 (4.10)
IVa	50	238	7.01 (7.29)
IVb	60	245	6.67 (6.79)
Va	65	260	7.03 (7.29)
Vb	70	251	6.65 (6.79)

* All compounds gave satisfactory analyses for C and H.

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL DATA OF γ -PYRONES OF COUMARINS (VI, VII)

Compound	Yield %	m.p. °C	Analysis% ; Found/(Calcd.)	
			C	N
VIa	80	285	74.01 (73.93)	4.25 (4.19)
VIIb	65	290	70.93 (70.80)	4.39 (4.34)
VIIa	68	265	73.99 (73.93)	4.27 (4.29)
VIIb	70	257	70.96 (70.80)	4.38 (4.34)

References

- SPATH, *Ber.*, 1937, 70A, 83.
- F. PATRICK, D. A. TIMONEV and M. A. VICKARAS, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, 24, 4941.
- A. C. ANNIGERI and S. SIDDAPPA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1964, 2, 413.
- T. OKUDA, J. KITAMIR and K. A. AZIKA, *Proc. Gifu Coll. Pharm.*, 1955, 2033.
- C. CARADONNA and M. L. STEIN, *Pharmaco. Educ. Sci.*, 1960, 15, 674.
- N. STELGER, *U. S. Patent*, 2,555,644; *Chem. Abs.*, 1951, 45, 10259.
- H. APPEL, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1031.
- A. A. SHAMSHUMER, *Univ. Sorb.*, 1939, 15, 33; *Chem. Abs.*, 1944, 3994.
- D. E. LIMAYE, *Rasayanam*, 1936, 420.
- A. RUSSUL and J. R. FRYE, *Org. Synth.*, 1941, 2122; *Chem. Abs.*, 1941, 6249.
- S. M. SETHANA, N. M. SHAH and R. C. SHAH, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 228.